

Legal Perspective of the LGBTQ Community in India : An Analysis

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Abstract

This research examines underappreciated yet crucial aspects of mankind. Shikhandi, a warrior in ancient literature, contributed significantly to the Mahabharata triumph. This research aims to explore the socio-legal experiences of the LGBTQ community in India and how their rights and protection have been impacted by collective efforts. Morality of other members of society. This research focuses on individuals who identify as third-gender and have a sexual orientation such as lesbian, gay, or bisexual. This research focuses on the contemporary socio-legal condition of the subject topic and includes historical sources. This study examines how the Indian Constitution's concept of equality and non-discrimination applies to sexual orientation and gender identity. In mythology, gods like Hermaphroditus redefined human existence and non-binary love. Malik Kafur, a companion and confidante of Alauddin Khilji played the most significant role in the annexation of other empires. Although resilience is important for promoting LGBTQ health, there is still more work to be done before it can be effectively measured. Lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer (LGBTQ) health research has traditionally focused mainly on the hazards of poor health outcomes, masking the methods in which LGBTQ communities maintain and enhance their health throughout the life cycle. In this study, we propose that establishing culturally appropriate health policy. This necessitates moving the evidence base of LGBTQ health research away from deficit-focused approaches. Towards strengths-based methods to understanding and assessing LGBTQ health.

Keywords: LGBTQ, Health promotion, Health measurement.

Introduction

The entire universe is perceived through the lens of binary focus. A day is made up of alternating light and darkness. Emotions are made up of fluctuating states of happiness and sadness. Sky and ground, the Oxymorons such as "dry and wet," "real and unreal," "right and left," and "life and death" can lead to feelings of fulfilment and contentment. We still feel incomplete and dissatisfied since our subconscious suggests the morning, indifference, horizon, dampness, surreal, centre, and notional area of uncertainty. This study focuses on the similarities and differences in anatomy and psychology between men and women. This study examines a sometimes overlooked but equally important topic. Research on LGBTIQ health increasingly emphasises resilience. Although there is no universally accepted definition of resilience, although it typically refers to the capacity to tolerate or overcome substantial stress or hardship.

Concept

LGBT stands for "Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender". This term refers to individuals whose sexual orientation or gender identification differs from the majority of society's norms. L, G, and B allude to individuals with various sexual orientations than heterosexuals, while T represents those who think their gender identity differs from the gender given at birth.

In 1869, Hungarian writer Károli Mária Kertbeny invented the terms "homosexual" and "homosexuality" in a political dissertation against Paragraph 143, a Prussian statute that was subsequently codified in Germany's Paragraph 175, which criminalized male homosexuality.. Kertbeny's view that homosexuality¹ is inborn and immutable serves as a counterpoint to the condemnatory sentiments that contributed to the introduction of sodomy legislation. He argues that it is a normal variation. The history of homosexuality dates back to the mid-19th century, with Karl Heinrich² Ulrichs' book being particularly significant. He was a Master of Law, Theology, and History, and is regarded as one of the first advocates for LGBT rights in contemporary history. He produced a series of socio-political writings against discriminatory legislation.

To better understand LGBT rights, it's important to first identify who these individuals. To accurately describe LGBTs, researchers must first define sexuality, sexual orientation, and gender identity. This ensures a clear understanding of the often misunderstood term.

The term "sexuality" has numerous meanings. The meaning of this phrase varies by each interpretation. Sexuality is commonly defined as a collection of actions, sentiments, or classifications based on sexual orientation, identity, or politics allegiances.³ In a similar vein, "the plural, sexualities, is utilised to acknowledge the multiple meanings of sexuality and to recognise that an understanding of contemporary sexuality needs to engage with a proliferation of identity categories sexual practices, subjectivities, desires and relationship formations, including for example queer or transgender alongside more familiar categories such as heterosexual, lesbian, gay and bisexual."⁴ Although the phrase is wide, it lacks exact definitions.

Sex- A person's sex is determined by bodily characteristics such chromosomes, gonads, hormones, reproductive systems, and genitalia.⁵

Gender- Gender is determined by a person's actions, interactions, and feelings, which are associated with boys/men and girls/women, rather than their sex.⁶

According to the Yogyakarta Principles, sexual orientation refers to an individual's strong emotional, loving, and sexual attraction to and personal relationships with others. Different gender, same gender, or more than one gender".⁷ It also refers to a long-term emotional, romantic, or sexual attraction to individuals of either gender.

Heterosexuality refers to being attracted to someone of the opposite sex, as opposed to homosexuality. Lesbians - Lesbian refers to a woman who has both physical and sexual attraction to another woman. Although this definition appears to be accurate at first glance, further investigation reveals flaws, abnormality because it classifies even bisexual women as lesbians. The phrase originated in the 16th century to allude to Lesbos, a Greek island, and was associated with "female homosexuality" in the 19th century.⁸ The word "lesbian" lacks a uniform definition, with researchers identifying women based on various criteria.

Gay- Homosexuality refers to a person's physical, emotional, and sexual attraction to someone of the same gender. Previously, the term "homosexual" was often used to characterise those with same-sex orientation. In recent years, the term "gay" has replaced "homosexual" to describe individuals with different sexual orientations. The origins of the term "gay" are unclear, and its incorporation into the English language remains a source of debate. The term "playboy" was initially used in the 18th century in England to describe the behaviour of a playboy. It later became popular in the in the 19th century, the term "prostitute" referred to women of loose morals.⁹ In 1933, Noel Ersines produced the Dictionary of Underworld and Prison Slang, which popularised the word in the US. The term "gay" was published as "geycat". Previously, the term "gay" was used to refer to all homosexuals, but is now more specific and is used to denote a male homosexual.

Bisexuals are sexually attracted to both sexes. Bisexuality is defined as having physical, emotional, or other attraction to individuals of the same or opposite gender. It's not easy. Bisexual individuals are often overlooked in society since they are classified as heterosexual while in a sexual connection with someone of the opposite gender and gay when in a same-sex relationship. Bisexual people face prejudices due to their ability to have sexual relationships with both sexes.

Gender identity differs from sexual orientation. Yogyakarta Principles define gender identity as an individual's internal and subjective sense of gender, which may or may not align with sex. At birth,

individuals are given a personal perception of their body, which may be modified by medical or surgical procedures if desired. Gender expression may take several forms, such as attire, voice, and mannerisms. In essence, gender identity refers to a person's perception of themselves. Transgender individuals are defined as those whose gender identity or expression differs from their given sex at birth.

Transgender - Magnus Hirschfeld, a well-known German sexologist, first created the terms 'transvestites' and 'transsexuals' in the early 1900s.³¹ In 1919, he created the Institute for Sexual Science in Berlin, which was later demolished by the Nazis in 1933.

It is worth noting that he was a homosexual.³² Virginia Prince coined the term "transgenderism," which encompasses both transsexualism and transvestism. He also wrote novels like "Understanding." Cross-dressing and seventy years in the battlefields of the gender wars." "Transgender is an umbrella term for people whose gender identity, gender expressions, and/or behaviours are different from those culturally associated with the sex to which they were assigned at birth."

LGBT - This acronym "combines two letters (L and G) that specify the terms for male and female same-sex desire, while adding two letters (B and T) that assign forms of sexual embodiment." Expressions that are not always based on a stable or containable identity." The term "LGBT" emerged during the sexual revolution in the 1960s and has since become a part of current terminology. The sexual revolution began in the 1960s and peaked in the United States. The uprising was a response to society rules that pushed people to conform and repress their natural desires.

Families' attitudes towards LGBT individuals are influenced by society's acceptance or rejection of homosexuality and non-binary gender. Advocacy groups and civil society activists launched a large awareness campaign. CSOs can help eliminate the stigma associated with alternative gender identities and sexual orientations. CSOs and advocacy groups play a crucial role in furthering the rights of LGBT people in nations where religious orthodoxy is prevalent. Governments in democratic frameworks may be hesitant to do so for fear of losing popular support.

The LGBT community had significant challenges between 2020 and 2021. The global COVID-19 epidemic has caused unprecedented damage to the community. The economic downturn around the world. The effects of the epidemic has disproportionately impacted the community. Covid-19 has had a psychological impact on the community, in addition to its economic and physical costs. The Kaiser Family Foundation conducted a poll in the United States where LGBT households experienced greater rates of job loss during the COVID-19 pandemic than non-LGBT families, with more than half reporting this experience. LGBT persons are more likely than non-LGBT people to experience stress and worry about the coronavirus. Additionally, three-quarters of LGBT people are concerned about contracting the virus.

Legal Prospective

In India, the Supreme Court repealed Victorian-era Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code in the historic *Navtej Singh Johar v. Union of India* decision, allowing consenting gay adults to engage in sexual conduct.

They are only at the beginning since they do not have a fundamental right such as the right to marry. As a result, same-sex couples are denied social and legal recognition. Although the Supreme Court's decision to decriminalise homosexuality in the Johar case was a positive step, the government should now accept homosexuality.

Legalising gay marriages in conservative countries may be challenging due to societal attitudes against homosexual unions. However, in a democratic polity, legislators must consider societal attitudes. Article 44 of the Constitution states that the State is responsible for ensuring a uniform civil code for citizens across India's territory.

LGBT individuals experience marginalisation at several levels, including family, schools, institutions, and businesses. LGBT people are generally marginalised, resulting in limited financial resources and low-wage employment opportunities. LGBT individuals are among the most workplace discrimination may negatively impact marginalised groups in society. As a result, they are more likely to experience

unemployment and poverty. LGBT individuals often drop out of education owing to social discrimination, limiting their economic potential.

Affirmative action, including reservations for LGBT individuals in educational institutions and government positions, can provide a solid revenue source for them. In 2014, the Supreme Court of India issued the momentous NALSA ruling, which mandated the Central. In the past seven years, state administrations have not made any real efforts to offer reservation for transgender individuals in education or employment.

LANDMARK JUDGEMENT

In the NAZ foundation case, the court deemed some portions of Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code invalid and decriminalised same-sex sexual conduct between consenting adults, providing a boost to the LGBT population in India. In *Naz Foundation v. Government of NCT of Delhi (2009)*¹⁰, the court ruled that criminalising same-sex sexual actions between consenting adults in private violates their dignity, discriminates against them, and negatively affects their health. The Delhi High Court stated that "the sphere of privacy allows individuals to develop human relationships without interference from the outside community or the state." The Delhi High Court further said that, "The area of privacy empowers people to create interpersonal relationships without intervention from the outside community or the State. The practice of autonomy allows an individual to achieve fulfilment and progress in self-esteem, develop relationships of his or her choosing, and achieve all valid goals that he Alternatively, she may set. In the Indian Constitution, the right to live with dignity of privacy are both accepted as elements of Article 21. Section 377 of the IPC breaches Article 21 of the Constitution by denying a person's dignity and criminalising their essential identity based on their sexuality. According to Article 21 of the Constitution, the 377 IPC violates the right to full personality for LGBT people.

In 2013, the Indian Supreme Court ruled that section 377 of the IPC does not violate constitutional requirements in *Suresh Koushal v. Naz Foundation*, overturning the historic ruling. In the past 150 years, just a few individuals have been booked under this section. The Supreme Court decriminalised homosexual sex by removing Section 377 from the Indian Penal Code, leaving it up to the government and legislature. In December 2013, the Supreme Court deemed s. 377 of the Indian Penal Code to be constitutional. However, many groups, including the Naz Foundation, filed review petitions against the ruling. The court's decision to send curative petitions to the Constitution bench supports LGBT advocates' claims of a miscarriage of justice in the Naz case. The foundation ruling overturned the landmark 2009 Delhi High Court decision.

In 2017, a nine-judge court led by the Chief Justice of India proclaimed privacy a fundamental right guaranteed by the Indian Constitution. This was a significant victory for LGBT individuals. The Supreme Court overturned previous rulings in the M.P. Sharma and Kharak Singh cases from 1958 and 1961, respectively. The LGBT community was pleased with the privacy judgement, which found that s.377 had a "chilling effect" on privacy and threatened the unhindered fulfilment of one's sexual orientation as an element of privacy and dignity. The judges also recognised that sexual orientation is an important aspect of privacy.

THE TRANSGENDER PERSONS (PROTECTION OF RIGHTS) ACT¹¹

In 2019, the Indian parliament approved the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act to safeguard the rights of transgender individuals. Their welfare, as well as issues linked with and incidental to it. "The 255 Act is a positive step towards equality for transgender individuals, however its implementation is challenging due to various gaps. The Act uses a single definition of "transgender" without distinguishing between transgender, transsexual, and intersex individuals. While the Act prohibits discrimination against transgender individuals, the lack of an institutional mechanism to enforce these provisions weakens the legislation. The absence of enforceability of transgender provisions, along with a general lack of understanding, renders the act ineffective. The planned National Council for Transgender Persons should have more transgender representation, as it now only includes five community representatives and numerous union ministers. To improve inclusivity, progressive provisions should be included in addition to the identified gaps. Argentina's Gender

Identity Law is largely regarded as the most comprehensive law on transgender persons, allowing for easy identity changes without cumbersome procedures. Art. 3 of the statute states that anybody can seek the recorded intercourse.

In the *Navtej Singh Johar*¹² case, the Supreme Court repealed Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code (IPC), making all consensual sex among adults, including gay intercourse, legal. In the *NALSA*¹³ case, the court recognised transgender people's freedom to choose their gender and directed the Centre and state governments to legally recognise their gender identification as male, female, or third gender.

Conclusion

Despite Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights stating that "all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights," LGBT individuals continue to face discrimination. Our society's deeply ingrained homophobic and transphobic attitudes have led to significant inequality and discrimination. LGBT people face prejudice compared to their non-LGBT peers. Widespread harassment, ostracism, and violence. Homophobia and transphobia are not only economic issues in developing countries. LGBT people face prejudice in both developed and developing nations. Collaboration between worldwide LGBTQIA+ groups and local associations can help LGBTQIA+ people connect with community-based sexual health services and support networks. Until recently, little has been known about the issues that occur when digital technology and LGBTQIA+ rights intersect. There is minimal scholarly agreement on disciplinary approaches or a shared terminology for this understudied area. To address the issues at the intersection of LGBTQIA+ rights and digital technology, a variety of academic and multidisciplinary techniques can be applied, including sociological, psychological, philosophical, and economic ones.

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